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Repositioning Teacher Education: Strategy for Equipping the Nigerian Child with Skills and Competencies to Succeed in the Competitive Global Community

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ABSTRACT

The past decade has seen globalization and emerging technologies fundamentally transforming every society (developing and developed alike) by creating a knowledge economy that influences the way people live and interact with one another. Obviously, the teacher is quite conversant with the processes of education, growth and development. The standard of education in a country is largely a function of the quality of its teachers in the educational system. Such teachers must be endowed with the spirit of enquiry, creativity and can fit properly into the global community. It is therefore essential that nations provide their children with an education that prepares them to participate and adapt to a rapidly changing global competitive environment, where an average student will have multiple careers before retirement. It is through teacher education that teachers for the global child will be educated; hence this process should be revamped towards the demand of globalization. This paper offers challenge for a re-position in the new wave of globalization by reviewing the policies of education to include a sound programme of Teacher Education that will emphasize and incorporate global demands of the Nigerian child.

Key words: Repositioning teacher education, Nigeria, teacher competencies, global competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization has unified the entire world into one small village with common educational system, so that people nowadays frequently talk about the world educational systems. The system is characterized by information, skills and orientation (ISO); hence, many refer to this as "information society". The teacher remains the pivot in a knowledge-driven society as he has the primary responsibility of transmitting ISO from generation to generation, be it in Science, Mathematics, Arts, History, Religion, Business, etc. This is further explained by the statement of the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) that none of these fields can advance beyond the quality of the teachers. Aware of the role of the teacher in educational and national development, the Federal Government of Nigeria made efforts to improve teacher training policies and practices across levels of education through the provision of the National Teacher Education Policy (NTEP, 2004, 2009).

The NTEP gives emphasis to teacher education for educational planning and development as a way of assisting the nation to meet educational goals including Education For All (EFA) and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The realization of vision 20-20 whose ideals are aimed at making Nigeria one of the largest economies in the world, able to consolidate its leadership role in Africa and establish itself as a significant player in the global economic and political arena, is hinged on a well-structured teacher education policy. According to the policy, the objective of the teacher education is to provide highly motivated, conscientious and resourceful classroom teachers for all levels of the Nigerian Educational System; teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their obligation and make them adaptable to changing situations. Given these requirements, it is expected that teacher education products should demonstrate some degree of competencies as they carry out their tasks.

Evidently, teachers playing a fundamental role in the educational delivery process can only give what they have. A number of authors have converged in expressing concern that the present educational opportunities offered to learners at the basic, secondary and tertiary education levels seem to be lacking in meeting the objective of teacher education (Obioma, 2010; Durosaro, 2010; Adah, 2011 and Amadi, 2011). For instance, Madumere-Obike lamented that: The present-status of secondary education in Nigeria only enables our teaching products to acquire knowledge and facts with little understanding, without useful skills and orientation that can lead them to self-actualization. This practice has given rise to the current wave of youth restiveness, unemployable graduates, with a good number involving themselves in armed robbery, reckless destruction of lives and properties, hooliganism, prostitution and political thuggery (Osuwa, 2006).

It is therefore, evident that teacher education and development can be a singular factor that can clog the wheel of progress in any nation's development. An informed and effective teacher becomes a dynamic instrument of change and stability. Teacher quality must therefore, be genuinely and urgently addressed since the quality of teachers determines the quality of output. This is why professionals and teacher educators must seek strategies to repositioning teacher education and development. More so, as we strive to meet local needs, our teachers so produced must meet minimum global bench marks and best practices so as to make our learners compete favorably with their counterparts in the global arena.

Concept of Teacher Education

Generally, teacher education could refer to the exposure of learners to a body of knowledge, policy and procedures designed to equip prospective teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviours and skills they require to perform their task effectively in the classroom, the school and the wider community (Wikipedia, 2007). Even though Teacher Education prepares an individual to develop into a proficient teacher, anyone that is aiding others to learn, in a sense, is seen as the teacher. But teaching requires special skills, abilities put into practice to be an efficient teacher. Ngada (2005) sees teacher education as customized towards developing the individual to his full potential by contributing significantly to the necessities and aspirations of his society. It must be realistic, functional, and inculcate self-confidence in the student-teachers. The learning experience offered to learners must be justified on grounds of relevance. To accomplish this, the services in teacher education institutions ought to be extended to facilitate suitable training for the student teacher.

According to Ivowi (2000), reported in Adah, (2011), the competency of a teacher in terms of professional capacity should be anchored on the following:

1. Skill processes – facilitate the development and acquisition of appropriate manipulation skills in students; and also laboratory management techniques and workshop practices where applicable;
2. Subject matter – appropriate and relevant knowledge of facts, principles, concepts and laws needed to sustain cognitive knowledge of the students;
3. Behaviour motivation – through appropriate behaviour, mode of dressing, and reaction to stimuli in the normal course of interacting with students with a view to stimulating interest in them;
4. Resourcefulness – improvisation of teaching aids of relevant descriptions, some measure of discovery and maintenance/repairs of minor faults in laboratory apparatus, equipments and teaching aids;
5. Pedagogy – exposure and experience in principles and practice of education and in the art of teaching as an aid to meaningful learning;

Strategy for Repositioning Teacher Education in Nigeria

6. Evaluation – self and students' evaluation through appropriate construction of tests, their analysis and inference.

In other words, the overall quality of a teacher is wrapped up in the above professional skills. Teachers as professionals must realize the frequent changes in societal factor which detect changes in methodology and even the curriculum. Undoubtedly, teachers need a wide exposure of their content area in terms of experience and need to acquire other professional skills from the competitive market if they are to be effective in the discharge of their responsibilities.

In Nigeria, teachers engage in continuing education programmes such as, registering for sandwich or part time B.ED or distance education with the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) and National Teachers Institute (NTI). Other teachers, who already have university degrees and wish to update their skills and enhance their status, pursue continuing education through post graduate programmes in the universities and through in-service workshops, seminars and conferences.

Continuing education has become a tool with which teachers today, try to meet up with the prescription of the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN), a professional regulatory body that ensures that teachers pass teacher professional courses to equip themselves with competencies that qualify them for registration as professional teachers. A repositioning of teacher education to bring in effectiveness in ensuring that teachers mandatorily and on yearly basis, train and update their status is necessary as this could be the main source of professional and continuing development for many teachers. The educational system is long overdue in its efforts to usher in an effective teacher education policy that prepares teachers to become professionals after the kind of the developed climes, which provide foundation for the needed quality, effectiveness and relevance in education at all levels. There is no other time that this call can be more imperative than now.

Review of the Present Position of Teacher Education and Development in Nigeria

Before 1996, the minimum requirement for primary school teaching was the Grade 2 teachers certificate (TC II), though there still existed many teachers with primary school leaving certificates. With the advent of Universal Primary Education (UPE) in 1996, came an urgent need to raise teachers for the programme through the introduction of the 5-year post primary training and 1-year post-secondary education crash programme. In the course of time, these teachers became nonfunctional and ineffective to cope with emerging demands of the content and delivery processes of primary education. Thus, with the revision of the National Primary Education (NPE) in 1981,

government stipulated new minimum qualification for primary school teachers in 1996.

Later, a major reform in teacher education programme was recorded as 3-year plan was set for phasing out Grade two teacher training colleges and Grade two certificate holders. As laudable as this policy appeared, Obioma (2010) identified a number of implementation gaps, prominent among them were:

1. Continuous shift in the time lines due to inability of some states, especially in the north to completely phase out the old regime;
2. Inability of Colleges of Education (that produced pre-service NCE teachers) to promptly review their programme to produce adequate and functional primary school teachers;
3. Though the National Teachers Institute (NTI) as part of its statutory responsibilities upgrades serving primary school teachers to NCE holders, the post training performance of school teachers has come under criticism in terms of quality output. Obviously, these and other challenges became eminent in the teacher education programmes.

Effort to meet with the challenges of teacher education in Nigeria, led the Federal Government to formulate a national policy on teacher education in 2009, with the objective of providing a road map for teacher educators in Nigeria. According to the New National Teacher Education Policy, the Nigeria Certificate of Education (NCE) became the minimum standard for primary school teachers. In addition, the relevant government authorities in support of national Information Technology (IT) vision of 2005, and based on the need for ICT in teaching-learning process, made the acquisition of basic ICT skills and capabilities part of the minimum standards for both NCE and First Degrees in Education as issued by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE). National Universities Commission (NUC) and the Teachers' Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN).

Presently, the mode of teacher preparation that permits primary school teachers to be assigned to individual classes where a classroom teacher is expected to cope with up to 12 subjects has been seen to be deficient when weighed against the expectations and demands of globalization (Obioma, 2010). Even when the pre-service teachers opting for NCE were exposed to new content area (curriculum) that would bring flexibility in their teaching, on graduation, qualifying teachers were deployed to teach individual classes and all subjects as was obtainable in the old system. This practice has persisted to date thus, producing NCE holders who cannot cope with the demands of the present primary school teaching. The problem has been compounded by the fact that the pre-service teachers dabbled into teaching as not only transitory but as last resort; therefore, from the onset, they appear to be disenchanted and ill-motivated.

Teacher education lacks developmental framework that could lead to improvement in service delivery like other professions. For example,

Strategy for Repositioning Teacher Education in Nigeria

opportunities like in-service training and strategic capacity building which can lead to promotion and enhancement of status are merely regarded as favour and privileges. This is why teachers' salaries and conditions of service are still very deplorable.

As part of the repositioning in teacher education, the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) proposed the 9-year Basic Education Curriculum Programme (BEC) for pre-secondary education and the 3-year Senior Secondary Education Curriculum (SSEC) which were approved then by NCE in December 2005 and 2006 respectively. However, the implementation that was to take place in 2011 was delayed up to September last year, 2013 when it was publicly presented. With these reforms in the content standard of pre-secondary and tertiary education, the question is, has any impact been made on teacher education?

Fundamental to the success of these content standard reforms, lays the critical issue of producing qualified teachers to teach the new curricula and with particular regards to the new subject matter introduced at both basic and senior secondary education levels. Teaching being at the heart of education, any nation therefore, wishing to bring a significant improvement in education, must strengthen the teaching profession. With the changes in curriculum, it is imperative that quality teacher programmes and policies related to selection, training, certification, hiring and retention of good teachers be put in place.

Unfortunately, Obioma (2010) noted that the curriculum reform has not been efficiently followed up at the teacher education programmes of colleges of education, polytechnics and universities. He noted that the regulatory efforts of the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) to drive review of NCE programme in line with minimum content standard of 9-year BEC are not comprehensive and far reaching enough. For instance, a subject like integrated science that is being taught in colleges of education has long been replaced by Basic Science. In the same way, Basic Science and Technology and Basic Technology have replaced Primary Science and Introductory Technology while pre-service teacher, NCE teachers lack exposure in subject matter like computer studies which are obtainable in the new 9-year BEC. With the new 34 Technical/Entrepreneurship subjects structure of the SSEC, there is very little evidence to support that teacher educators in the tertiary institutions have made adequate preparation to accommodate content structure and delivery processes. Both the teacher and the learner are still seen as "storage banks". In this case, the learner is taught to accept everything the teacher says, and therefore, there is no room for creative thinking. There is therefore, the need to re-examine the present teacher education thus, the re-envisioning paradigm.

A. Trends in Global Teacher Education

Global economy growth has created a sense of urgency leading to calls for re-positioning our approach to education and training which is a critical

component of national economic competitiveness. Globalization is not merely an economic phenomenon; it is multidimensional. It affects every aspect of our lives: politics, trade, leisure and education etc. it is fuelled by knowledge and it is a key factor driving the changes we witness and experience today. Globalization is founded on and empowered by education, formal and informal and the speed and intensity depend on the quality and product of education (Nenty, 2010). It is characterized by quests for information, innovation, creativity and agility. Nations that have embraced the emerging technologies, particularly information and communication technology are the ones experiencing these unprecedented global economic growths.

It is hardly difficult for these nations to survive without developing the skills of its teachers, the values and approaches of the competitive market. This is because the quality and type of global teacher education determines the quality of human resources in all other sectors of the economy. To this end, global schools are therefore, being challenged to produce students who are knowledge producers, problem solvers and creative thinkers. These are students who are able to use high level thinking skills, which are essential for generating knowledge that enriches people's lives (Cummings, 2013). According to Bottery (1989), global teacher education is to promote practices of accountability, quality control, efficiency of performance and customers' satisfaction. It is to address issues and challenges such as climates change and population, poverty reduction, reduction of fossil consumption, reduction of risk, disaster and terrorism, HIV/AIDS and other diseases as well as issues that cloud the global community. This implies that teacher education should be re-positioned to meet the need of globalization.

B. Expectations of a Global Teacher/Child

In the contemporary society, globalization has created unprecedented challenges that put a teacher in a position whereby he is required to undertake a complex set of tasks on daily basis. These tasks no longer consist in production of the local child who lacks knowledge, skills and attitudes needed to survive, compete and contribute to the development of the global and local economy. The task of teaching a global child is demonstrated when this child is taught for tomorrow's technology-driven world.

The Nigerian global teacher, educating for globalization is expected to lay emphasis on the teaching and learning of international language especially the language of technology. Therefore, the global teacher must have a high knowledge of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) or computer and internet literacy, a good knowledge of world geography; history of civilization; democracy and good governance; a good level of appreciation of cultural and individual diversity and learning to live together in peace with others; functions and the role of international organizations; all

Strategy for Repositioning Teacher Education in Nigeria

aspects of human rights and privileges and a good level of acquaintance with major global problems (Rassekh, 2001).

The goal of a globalised teacher is to empower the child by developing his/her skills, learning and other capacities, human dignity, self esteem and confidence. In other words, he should carry education beyond normal schooling to embrace the broad range of life experience and learning processes that will enable children, individually and collectively to develop their personalities, talents and abilities to live a full and satisfying life in the community (UN, 2001, par. 3).

A global teacher has a child under him who has the world to compete with. He should see the child as such. The technology-driven "image of the child that dominates media, science and policy today is not valued for who he/she is, but what he/she can become" (Pence & Hix-Small, 2009, p 1). Therefore, the education of the globalised child is not discriminatory but calls for quality, access and equity. Globalization insists on lifelong education of the total person through the provision of environment rich enough to enable the un-packaging and development of every learner. The emphasis of a global teacher is to balance the three domains of learning (cognitive, affective and psychomotor).

According to Stewart (2007), the global child requires skills to enable him/her to:

- Sell his developed potentials to the world through internet;
- Buy from the world;
- Work for international companies from the home and make multiple streams of income;
- Manage employees from other countries and cultures;
- Compete with people from the other side of the world for job and market;
- Work with people all over the world in joint ventures and global work teams;
- Contribute solutions to global problems such as HIV/AIDS, flu, environmental problem and conflict resolution.

Professionally, an effective global child teacher is one that shows maximum commitment to the success of the child in every aspect of life. Similarly, Tang (2008) observed that teachers of the global child should be:

- A skilled and knowledgeable practitioner, with an enquiry-based mode of teaching and the one that uses feedback in a variety of assessment methods to enhance performance;
- A proficient thinker and problem solver, able to use applied reflective assessment and evaluation technique to maximize student learning;
- With a high level cultural awareness and appreciation and the ability to transmit same to his student;
- With a high level of world event and global dynamics and ability to ensure student understanding of and perspective of such issues;

- One with high level of e-capabilities (technology/internet literacy for the 21st century);
- A responsible and ethical citizen in the respect of learners' right and accept responsibilities as a global citizen;
- Teach and has the ability to develop similar capacity in his students.

Nenty (2010), emphasized that the mission of any teacher training programme should be to develop these characteristics in teacher trainees. In other words, lessons should be prepared and taught with the world in mind in order to develop a globally competent learner with wide and global worldview.

Repositioning Teacher Education in Nigeria

As part of the recommendation, this paper shall identify some useful lessons and opportunities for improving teacher education and development in Nigeria. Nigerian education has undoubtedly assumed the position as the most fundamental instrument for national development (FGN, 2004). Successive governments have formulated educational policies and carried out reforms aimed at reshaping teacher education and development in such a way as to bring transformation in all aspects of the nation's economy. However, a review of the general trend in the Nigerian teacher educational reform shows that much of what has been done has remained structural at best. This paper will identify some useful lessons to be learnt as given by Osioma, (2011) and suggest opportunities for improving teacher education for development in Nigeria.

Poor implementation of public policies in teacher education has resulted into their imminent collapse. The UPE post primary and post secondary programmes are good examples. With poor implementation, the individual student for which education is meant for is left out. Achieving a learner's education requires a repositioning the Nigerian educational system and conducting a reform that takes into consideration the lessons learnt from other nations particularly the Asian nations of Singapore and Finland.

Singapore

- With knowledge-based economy as the driver in the global community, Singapore sees education as a key in the growth and development of Singaporean society.
- Evolved from its traditional British-based educational system to the one that meets individual needs and nurture talents.
- Every child/individual can realize his potentials to benefit the community, nation and lead a personality fulfilling life.

Strategy for Repositioning Teacher Education in Nigeria

- Through curriculum reform policy enacted in 1997 by the Singaporean government, in addition to marketization of education policy, creativity and innovation has been the watchword.
 - Curriculum reform launch led to three major initiatives which government saw as crucial to the Singaporean national effort to remain competitive in the midst of the growing global knowledge economy. The three initiatives are:
1. **The Thinking School, Learning Nation Initiative** – focused on developing all students into active learners with critical thinking skills, and a creative and critical thinking culture which must be developed within school. Four strategies employed to achieve the above include:
 - a. The explicit teaching of critical and creative thinking skills.
 - b. The reduction of subject contents.
 - c. The revision of assessment modes.
 - d. A greater emphasis on process rather than outcomes when appraising schools.
 2. **The Master Plan for Information Technology in Education Initiative** – focused on incorporating IT into teaching and learning in all schools with full implementation.
 - Initiative achieved through government funding of installation of physical infrastructures and training of pre- and in-service teachers: frequency of teachers re-training programmes.
 - Whole school networking installed, and schools received one computer for every two students and one note book for every two teachers.
 3. **The Revisions to the University Admission Criteria** – based on recommendations in 1999 of the Committee University Admission Systems that moved the criteria for admission into the university to go beyond the performance at the A-Level, GCE examination to include students' results of the national scholastic test and their results in project work at school and participation in extra-curricular activities in school.
 - Promoted innovation and creativity as this third initiative complemented the first.
 - Students' best benefited from the two enquiry approaches – student-directed enquiry and teacher-guided enquiry of teaching and learning.
 - As reported by the Third International Mathematics and Science Studies (TIMSS), Singapore's public schools have a unique record of high standards in teaching and learning.
 - Strength of Singaporean education system lies in its broad-based curriculum where innovation and entrepreneurship are the driving force.

Finland

- Small agrarian nation in the early 1960s and later drawn into capitalism and today has become a nation with one of the most effective educational systems.
- Has transformed their agrarian economy into a sophisticated technology-driven nation.
- Broad-based, all-round education, with emphasis on “whole child” and scientific literacy that equips the child with scientific knowledge, critical and rational thinking, and skills for future development.
- Goal-oriented teaching and learning with emphasis on social interaction among students and between students and teachers.
- High value and respect placed on teachers and their training aimed at learning to teach diverse learners for deep understanding.
- Great linkages as teachers work closely with universities, government agencies, community and business entities to create and revise curriculum. Teacher inputs are needed in scholarly forums.
- Finnish students today outperform peers and 43 others in assessment in science and mathematics skills and ranked top in economic competitiveness.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the above, as part of the effort to revamp teacher education in Nigeria for greater effectiveness and efficiency, there is need for the following:

1. The way of the future will ensure that implementation guidelines back up our planned policies as well as appropriate legislation. This best practice culture which reflects the policy situation in Singapore and Finland has led to the sustainability of their teacher education policy and the system of education as a whole.
2. The review of the primary and secondary school curricula should be equally matched with the repositioning of the training programmes of pre-service teachers. It is professionally impracticable to train primary school teachers to effectively teach all the primary school subjects in the 9-year BEC. The way forward is to reform teacher education by restructuring the training programme of pre-service teachers for specialization in related subject areas as best practiced in other developed countries (Finland, USA, Indonesia, etc) for global competitiveness.
3. The above implies shift in the way classroom transaction could be organized and managed. The pattern of rotating specialist primary teachers across streams of classes should be put in place and resources

Strategy for Repositioning Teacher Education in Nigeria

provided to support that, as this is what obtains in Britain, USA, India and Singapore. The persistent practice of assigning a teacher as an “all rounder” (handling up to 12 subjects), no longer meets emerging needs of global development of a Nigerian child.

4. Curriculum repositioning to promote interactive technology-based learning as in USA, Singapore, to promote collaborative skills, independent and confident learning and innovation.
5. Implementing the policy reform statements in the one-year strategy of restructuring and repositioning of NTI should be urgent as this will reinstate faith in the products of NTI.
6. There is need to reposition or reform the reformer. For success in any policy reform, the task of improving welfare and boosting morale of teachers must be addressed. Effort should be geared toward enhancing morale through improvement in incentive, work environment, social recognition, prompt payment of salaries and allowances.
7. Teacher education could be repositioned to include, Teacher Mentoring Scheme that will provide opportunity for freshly graduated teachers (Mentees) to be attached to senior teachers (Mentors) in their fields for at least one year to learn from the mentors’ wealth of experience. In addition, as it is done in the medical field, provision should be made for teachers’ “houseman ship” a period of at least one year internship/training before being fully engaged as a professional teacher.
8. The repositioning of teacher education could include a programme of exchange for teachers to visit other schools locally or outside their domain in order to be exposed to other areas and learn from situations in those areas. This exchange scheme obtains in universities as sabbatical leave.
9. Teacher education curriculum review – to accommodate global challenges such as language skills, numeric skills, ICT skills, population, HIV/AIDS, terrorism, child’s right, among others.
10. Review and match planned IT policy (Nigerian National Policy for Information Technology – NNPIT) with effective implementation guidelines to bring the vision of using ICT as the engine for sustainable development and global competitiveness to a reality. Government funding, commitment to frequent training/retaining of teachers including online teacher education, installation of whole school networking and reduced power outages as the way of the future.

CONCLUSION

Teacher education is a critical factor in national development. The essence of global repositioning in Nigeria teacher education is to create a new crop of

teachers with a deeper understanding of school subjects and endowed with the capacity to use their knowledge in handling all issues of global challenge. Such teachers would have therefore, imbibed the features of critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication, problem solving and continuous learning, enough to reproduce them in the Nigerian child. The simplest take-off point is to look at final models put in place by the developed nations such as United Nations, Britain, Singapore and Finland, etc, which have been successfully replicated by most developing countries.

REFERENCES

- Adah, S.A. (2011). Functional Teacher Education: A Sine Qua Non for poverty Reduction in Nigeria in Line with Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Paper presented at the 6th Annual National Conference of Association of Nigerian Teachers (ASSONT) held at Cross River State University of Technology, Calabar. August, 8th – 12th.
- Amadi, S. (2011). Global Education: Initiatives & Challenges. International Conference organized by Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Monday, 23rd May, 2011 at the Conference Auditorium, UNIZIK, Awka, Anambra State.
- Bottery, M. (1989). The Education of Business Management. *Oxford Review of Education*, 15 (2), 129-146.
- Cummings, G. (2013). Elementary and Secondary Education Act Reauthorization (2010). The US Department of Education. Retrieved on May 9th. Retrieved from: <http://www.ed.gov/blog/topic/esea-reauthorization/>
- Durosaro, D.O. (2010). Unionism, Quality Assurance and Productivity in Nigerian Higher Education System in J. B. Babalola., G. O. Akpa., A. O. Ayeni., and S. O. Adedeji., (Eds). Access, Equity and Quality in Higher Education, Ibadan, NAEAP.
- Federal Government of Nigeria (2004). The national policy on teacher education, Abuja, Federal Ministry of Education.
- Nenty, H.J. (2010). Teacher education for globalization in Nigeria. A paper presented at the 2nd International Conference organized by the Faculty of Education, University of Calabar, in corroboration with Teachers without Border, Seattle Washington, USA at the University of Calabar. May 7th – 10th.
- Ngada, J.A. (2000). Challenges and Future of Teacher Education in Nigeria. Multi Discipline Journal or Research Development. National University Commission: VIHEP Information Booklet 2005-2010.

Strategy for Repositioning Teacher Education in Nigeria

- Njoku, S. (2006). *ICT and Nigerian Teacher, Time to Catch up with the Rest of the world*. Abuja: TRCN.
- Obioma, G. (2010). *Reconstructing Polytechnic Education in Nigeria for the Attainment of Vision 20-20*. A Pre-Convention Lecture delivered at the 11th Convocation of the Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Uwana, Ebonyi State.
- Osuwa, C. (2006). *Teacher Capacity Building and Utilization, the Challenges of the 21st Century*. *Journal of Education Research and Development* 4 (2) 21-27. Singapore Education: Retrieved May, 2011 from <http://www.singapore.gov.sg/htm/abo01.htm>.
- Osisoma, R. (2011). *Re-imagining the Nigerian science and technical education: Equipping the Nigerian Child with the Skills and Competency to Succeed in the Competitive Global Community*. A Lead Paper presented at the 1st International Conference of the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. May 22nd – 28th.
- Pence, M. and H. Hix-Small, (2009). *Global Children in the Shadow of the Global Child International Critical Childhood Studies*. 2(1). Retrieved from <http://journals.sfu.ca/iccps/index.php/childhoods/article/viewFile/11/15>.
- Rassekh, S. (2001). *The Challenges facing Education and Curriculum Development at the Beginning of the Twenty-First Century*. In S. Rassekh, & J. Thomas (Eds.), *The Management of Curriculum Change and Adaptation in the Gulf Region*. Final Report of the Seminar held at Muscat, Oman International... Bureau of Education. The Omani National Commission for UNESCO retrieved from <http://www.ibe.unesco.org/fileadmin/userupload/archive/curriculum/GulfStatesProjectPdf/omanrep.pdf>.
- Stewart, V. (2007). *Globalization and education: Learning to compete in a new world*. *InternalizingMichigan Education*. Retrieved from <http://www.slideworld.org/.../Globalization-Education-learning-Compete-in-a-New-World-ppt-22519>.
- Tang, L. (N.D). *Teacher Perception for the Global Age. The Imperative for Change*. Lonview Foundation for Education in World Affairs and International Understanding, Inc. retrieved from <http://www.lonviewfdn.org/files/44.pdf>.
- United Nations (UN), (2001). *Conference on the Right of a Child. General Comment No. 1. The Aims of Education Article 29(1)*. Retrieved from <http://www.lonviewfdn.org/files/44.pdf>.
- Wikipedia (2007). *Teacher Education*. Retrieved July 27, 2014 from <http://en.wikipedia.org>.
- Wittenberg, A. (N.D). *The Prime Imperatives*. Toronto: Clark, Irwin. Reviewed from <http://www.holisticeducation.com/facilitator.htm>.